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FOR HERITAGE SCIENCE

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D2.5 Guidelines for the E-RIHS Central Hub Management Practices

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ABSTRACT

The document titled *E-RIHS IP D2.5 Guidelines for the E-RIHS Central Hub Management Practices* outlines the management practices for the E-RIHS ERIC Central Hub, located in Florence, Italy. The E-RIHS ERIC Central Hub hosts the legal seat and serves as the headquarters of the ERIC. It is regulated by the Article 19 of the E-RIHS ERIC Statutes and is managed by the Director General. It plays a crucial role in supporting the coordinated operations of E-RIHS ERIC by providing assistance to ensure its implementation. Its staff assists the Director General in the scientific, administrative, and financial coordination of the ERIC and the other governance bodies of E-RIHS ERIC, such as the General Assembly, the Committee of National Nodes, and the Scientific and Ethics Advisory Board. The guidelines described in this document are tailored to ensure efficient and coordinated operation of the distributed research infrastructure, in accordance with the legal requirements applicable to the operation of an ERIC. They cover some of the Central Hub's key operational practices, including service provision, training, communication, event organization, KPI monitoring, and Risk Management. The document also includes comparative analyses to benchmark the E-RIHS Central Hub's practices against other research infrastructures, offering elements for reflection and further adaptation. This deliverable is conceived as a living document, to be regularly updated and revised.

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviations	Expansion
CCSI	Cultural and Creative Sectors and Industries
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
CNN	Committee of National Nodes
CON	Communication Officers Network
CSA	Cooperative and Support Action
DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
DISSCo	Distributed System of Scientific Collections
DORA	Declaration on Research Assessment
EGI-ACE	EGI-Advanced Computing for EOSC
E-RIHS	European Research Infrastructure on Heritage Science
EHRI	European Holocaust Research Infrastructure
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
HS	Heritage Science
iCNN	Interim Committee of National Nodes
iGA	Interim General Assembly
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NN	National Node
OPERAS	European Research infrastructure for open scholarly communication in SSH
PRP	Peer Review Panel
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RIs	Research Infrastructure(s)
SMART	Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Time-bound

1 INTRODUCTION

The E-RIHS Central Hub serves as the headquarters and legal seat of the ERIC.

It is located in the former Manifattura Tabacchi premises in Florence, Italy. The site is an industrial heritage and is undergoing an urban regeneration project focused on art and creativity. As a part of this regeneration project, the Fondazione CR Firenze, a local foundation of banking origin, a non-profit entity (<https://fondazionecrfirenze.it/en/>), in a public-private partnership with the National Research Council of Italy (CNR), contributed to the acquisition and renovation of space for E-RIHS, which is the coordinator of the E-RIHS Italian Node through the Institute of Cultural Heritage Sciences that ensures the management and maintenance of these spaces, providing E-RIHS with rent-free premises as a host premium. Placing the E-RIHS Central Hub in the Manifattura Tabacchi enhances its operational environment with a unique blend of science and cultural dynamics. Manifattura Tabacchi is not just a workplace; it is a cultural center featuring artist residencies, a world-renowned fashion school, art exhibitions, etc. The placement of E-RIHS within this multifaceted context not only highlights its role in cultural heritage but also elevates its international stature, making it a crucial global meeting point for experts in both art and science. This strategic positioning underscores the importance of E-RIHS as a bridge between its cultural past and a creative future, shining a light on the interplay between culture, science, and innovation in contemporary society. The premises will count as host premium.

Central Hub of E-RIHS ERIC, regulated by the Statutes – Article 19, is managed by the Director General. Its activities support the coordinated operations of E-RIHS ERIC. As outlined in Article 19(7) of the E-RIHS ERIC Statutes, its staff assists the Director General in the scientific, administrative, and financial coordination of the ERIC. Additionally, it assists other governance bodies of E-RIHS ERIC, such as the General Assembly, the Committee of National Nodes, and the Scientific and Ethics Advisory Board (Figure 1).

Fig. 1: Organizational structure of E-RIHS ERIC

This document aims at providing guidelines for the management practices of the Central Hub activities. These practices are tailored to ensure efficient and coordinated operation of the distributed research infrastructure, as mandated by Article 2 and requested by Article 19(8) of the E-RIHS ERIC Statutes, in accordance with the legal requirements applicable to the operation of an ERIC.

The E-RIHS ERIC Central Hub serves as the base of operations for the distributed infrastructure, orchestrating the integrated activities of the comprising National Nodes and ensuring coordinated and efficient operations. It will enforce the governing policies, rules, and protocols thus maintaining consistency and coherence across the network. This centralized control ensures that the distributed infrastructure operates smoothly and achieves its objectives effectively. The Central Hub also serves as a communication nexus, allowing different parts of the distributed infrastructure to exchange data, information, and commands. It facilitates seamless communication between the nodes, enabling them to coordinate their activities effectively.

The Central Hub acts as the unique management access point to the resources distributed across the National Nodes. It supports the preparation of the portfolio of services listed in the E-RIHS Catalogue according to the four access platforms (ARCHLAB, DIGILAB, FIXLAB and MOLAB) and enables the centralized access to it. It assists National Nodes in ensuring adherence to quality standards and in coordinating the promotion of cross-disciplinary research and innovation, fosters international collaborations, and facilitates the provision of #HSAcademy training activities. It also aids in procuring funding opportunities. Furthermore, the Central Hub ensures that E-RIHS ERIC services are delivered effectively to users and manages coordinated efforts in communication and dissemination.

The E-RIHS ERIC tasks and activities and the Central Hub's role

The tasks and activities of E-RIHS ERIC, as described in Article 2 of the E-RIHS ERIC Statutes, guide the work of the Central Hub. The Central Hub, operating under the responsibility of the Director General, plays a crucial role in supporting these activities by providing coordination and assistance to ensure their effective implementation. Below, the main tasks and activities of E-RIHS ERIC are summarized.

The principal task of E-RIHS ERIC is to establish and operate the research infrastructure and coordinate its strategic and financial development. In pursuit of this principal task, and in accordance with the provisions of the Statutes, E-RIHS ERIC is dedicated to enabling and coordinating a community of National Nodes, including the establishment and monitoring of quality management procedures for the National Nodes and partner facilities. Additionally, it provides a central integrated access point to partner facilities and their resources based on scientific excellence, including continuous development and open access to material and digital scientific resources.

The organization supports the advancement of the scientific understanding of heritage and thus contributes to its conservation. It promotes Heritage Science, particularly its cross-disciplinary approach to research questions related to the history, interpretation, diagnosis, appreciation, and preservation of Heritage.

Furthermore, E-RIHS ERIC fosters a culture of cross-disciplinary and transnational collaboration by supporting researchers in developing comprehensive, advanced scientific and technological expertise, including training. It promotes innovation at the scientific and exploratory process, services, and management levels in Heritage Science, emphasizing technological interoperability and the convergence of methods through the definition of best practices.

In addition, E-RIHS ERIC may facilitate the mobility of researchers and other kinds of Users, identify European projects of interest in Heritage Science and related funding opportunities, and guide interested partners in their applications. It may establish international partnerships with other European and non-European organizations in Heritage Science and related fields and undertake any other activity necessary to fulfil its aims and objectives.

E-RIHS ERIC shall pursue all its activities ethically and transparently, avoiding potential organizational or personal conflicts of interest. It performs its tasks on a non-economic basis but, without prejudice to State aid applicable rules, may carry out limited economic activities provided they are closely related to its principal tasks and do not jeopardize their achievement. Any income generated by these economic activities is used by E-RIHS ERIC to enhance and strengthen its activities.

Director General and the Central Hub's role

The Central Hub supports the functions of the Director General, as defined in Article 19 of the E-RIHS ERIC Statutes. The Director General serves as the legal representative of E-RIHS ERIC and is responsible for implementing the decisions of the General Assembly. Additionally, the Director General must submit an annual activity report to the General Assembly, which takes into account the activities of the Committee of Nodes and the Scientific and Ethics Advisory Board. The Central Hub assists in these efforts, providing support to the Director General and the other governing bodies of E-RIHS ERIC, including the General Assembly, the Committee of National Nodes, and the Scientific and Ethics Advisory Board (see Figure 1). Both the Director General and the Central Hub are required to remain impartial in the performance of their duties.

2 E-RIHS CENTRAL HUB MANAGEMENT PROCEDURES

2.1 PROPOSED STRUCTURE OF CENTRAL HUB

E-RIHS ERIC management is supported by the staff operating at the Central Hub. The Human Resources (HR) strategy, recruitment process and the description of profiles are reported in E-RIHS IP D3.1 E-RIHS ERIC Human Resources Strategy and Procedures. As a general procedure for the staffing plan, the Director General (DG) will specify personnel requirements and the necessary financial coverage and present it to the General Assembly for discussion and approval (D3.1).

The Central Hub supports core E-RIHS ERIC activities on two levels:

1. **Operational:** support for externally visible core activities
2. **Internal:** operational and administrative support, such as HR, project management, planning and reporting.

The **Operational** activities are aimed at serving users and development of the E-RIHS ERIC as a label of quality. These include access-related activities, such as management of calls and services, user relationships, dissemination of results, organization of training, public engagement, international activities, and other communication and dissemination activities. Sub-functions operating at this level are: Access, International relations (including stakeholder relationship), HS Academy training initiatives and Communication.

The **Internal** activities include day-to-day management and administrative functions, scouting for external funding opportunities, support for project work such as administrative management of consortia and preparation of proposals. Further activities are E-RIHS ERIC quality assurance, Risk Management, HR, finance and accounting. This level includes the following sub-functions: Governance liaison flow, Access funds, Quality assessment, Risk Management, Legal affairs, Administration and financial management.

As a standard procedure for the staffing plan, the DG will specify personnel requirements and the necessary financial coverage and present it to the General Assembly for discussion and approval (D3.1). Within the staffing units, the Director General holds responsibility for appointing a data protection officer.

2.1.1 MAPPING EXERCISE OF RIS CENTRAL HUBS

Benchmarking analyses of other ERIC hubs explored the relation among the number of member countries (MC) and personnel at the Central Hub (Figure 2).

Fig. 2: Benchmarking analyses of the personnel at RI's Central Hubs

The data show that the SSH ERICs have lower personnel/member countries ratio (CESSDA, CLARIN, DARIAH) than the STEM ERICs (BBMRI, CERIC, EATRIS, ELIXIR). This suggests that the RIs that provide physical access for their users to the facilities need higher personnel/member countries ratio.

It is necessary to bear in mind that E-RIHS belongs to the SSH domain, but it is a combination of STEM and SSH expertise, providing mainly physical access to the facilities. Given the current 11 member countries that have confirmed their commitment to establishing E-RIHS ERIC in the Step 2 application, a **staffing level of approximately 16 personnel units** aligns with benchmarking analyses. This figure of 16 is derived from comparing the highest and lowest ratios of personnel to member countries across ERICs. Specifically, the highest ratio is 2,4, observed in ERICs providing physical access (e.g., CERIC), while the lowest ratio is 0,5, found in ERICs offering only digital data access (e.g., CESSDA). The resulting hypothetical ratio is 1,45, which, when applied to the number of E-RIHS member countries, suggests a need for 16 personnel units. This staffing level is consistent with other distributed ERICs, where most have an average of no more than 20 employees at their Central Hub (Source: ERIC Forum).¹

2.2 IMPLEMENTATION OF CENTRALIZED HELPDESK

To meet and manage the user's research needs, the Central Hub will operate through a unique User Helpdesk.

¹ See "Employment and Secondment." In *ERIC Forum*, <https://www.eric-forum.eu/toolkit/human-resources/employment-and-secondment/>. Accessed on 22/10/2024.

2.2.1 MAPPING EXERCISE OF RIS HELPDESKS

A mapping exercise of 45 through RIs and projects has been performed with the aim to analyse the RIs' landscape, identify benchmarks to take as model and identify elements to strengthen or to create in the future E-RIHS ERIC. In this perspective, the mapping exercise focused on several aspects concerning Help desk/Support office and the existence of:

- Dedicated office
- Dedicated platform
- Categories of support provided for users (Guidelines, FaQ, onsite service, etc.)

The mapping exercise highlighted that to define a User Helpdesk model, it is crucial to define available resources for helpdesk service in terms of the budget, tool, software and dedicated human resources. For example, as seen below an [open-source ticketing system](#) could be an interesting option to keep track of the different queries made to the helpdesk and to manage them.

Fig. 3: Survey of RI's – existence of User Helpdesk/Support Office (YES) vs. no service

The collected data (Figure 3) identified that only 64% of RI/Projects provide structured user support (27 out of 45 questioned RIs). Further detailed analyses focused on the categories of support provided to the users. Data below (Figure 4) show that most RIs rely on direct emailing – some in combination with the developed guidelines, fewer exploit Onsite Support (dedicated section on the website) and/or dedicated platform and only a few curate FaQ sections. It follows that, ideally, a combination of these tools should be implemented.

Fig. 4: Overview of support services offered by RIs to users

The mapping exercise evidenced that there exists a terminology conflict between “Helpdesk” and “User Support service” terms. Sometimes, these are used as synonyms, but in other cases, they refer to different or generic services. An example of a Helpdesk system implemented by DARIAH ERIC is reported in more detail as follows (Figure 5).

DARIAH ERIC operates a dedicated Helpdesk on its website through helpdesk software developed in partnership with CLARIAH-DE (CLARIN-D & DARIAH-DE). It offers a contact form and relies on the **Open-Source Ticket Request System (OTRS)** that can be integrated into WordPress. This open-source software is available on the DARIAH ERIC Github repository. DARIAH has opted for the OTRS ticketing system based on the good experience of its partners (Huma-Num, MAN Poznan, GWDG). The DARIAH Helpdesk contact form is organized into 7 categories, managed by several persons in charge (responsible role) as follows (Table 1).

Fig. 5: DARIAH-EU Helpdesk contact form with controlled list

Table 1: DARIAH-EU Helpdesk contact form with subject controlled list and associated responsible role

Category	Responsible role
Educational and training	DARIAH VCC2 co-chair
General	Outreach and Communications Officer
Join DARIAH	Secretary General
Open Science	Open Science Officer
Technical issues	Developer, Research Associate
Tools and Services	Developer, Research Associate
Working Groups	Chief Implementation Officer Team

Most of mature RIs run customized helpdesk systems equipped with ticketing system as can be found in the examples in the table below.

Table 2: Example of Helpdesk systems equipped with ticketing system

Project/RI	Software/ Tool/Plugin	Prize/year
DARIAH EU https://www.dariah.eu/helpdesk/	DARIAH EU + CLARIAH-DE created open source software, available on Github , integrable on Wordpress and capable of running the OTRS Ticketing System	ND
DiSSCo – Helpdesk https://dissco.jitbit.com/helpdesk	Jitbit (SaaS) https://www.jitbit.com/saas-helpdesk/purchase/	(€1.560/year for a company account with 7 agents).
EOSC Helpdesk operates at several support levels	https://eosc-helpdesk.eosc-portal.eu/help/en-us/10-for-eosc-providers-and-communities/6-what-is-eosc-helpdesk-and-what-benefits-it-provides-for-eosc-community based on Zammad , an open-source software with: contact form on the website, email (help@eosc-portal.eu)	
BBMRI ERIC ELSI helpdesk	https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/elsi/helpdesk/ https://www.bbmri.it/en/negotiator/adesione-al-servizio-bbmri-eric-negotiator/	
EATRIS	https://eatris.eu/services/innovation-helpdesk/#acc2	

2.2.2 MUST, SHOULD, COULD, WOULD (MoSCoW) CONSIDERATIONS ON HELPDESK SERVICE

Some considerations for the implementation of the helpdesk are summarized through a MoSCoW analysis in the table below (Table 3).

Table 3: MoSCoW analysis of helpdesk service

Must	Should	Could	Would
Ticketing system	Automated workflows (first automatic answer, notifications...)	Dedicated Responsible Person(s)	CRM - Customer Relationship Management adapted to Heritage Science services
Mail helpdesk	Guidelines for different kinds of users or services	Helpdesk network	
Tracking and automatic answers	Chat-bot (with an automatic answer)	Customizable	
Guidelines	Website Main menu: 'Help' and Dedicated pages for each issue/service/support	Analytics and insight tools	
Constantly updated FaQ section	Email import	Systematic Feedback by users	
User-friendly website	Group email distribution		
Answer within 24H	Dedicated Budget		
Follow up – Feedback (obligatory)			

2.3 PROVISION OF SERVICES

The Central Hub will assist in managing and allocating resources across the distributed infrastructure. It will monitor resource usage, optimize resource allocation based on demand and availability, and ensure efficient utilization of resources across the RI.

2.3.1 PROCEDURAL CONSISTENCY ACROSS THE PLATFORMS

Regarding the provision of services, **the following procedural consistency** will regard the three access platforms (ARCHLAB, FIXLAB, MOLAB):

- synchronized calendar of calls for proposals,
- **unified evaluation criteria** adopted by Peer Review Panels (PRP), composed of acknowledged experts in charge of the scientific evaluation and ranking of all TNA submissions,
- **integrated timing and documentation** of the selection procedure,
- **a dedicated centralized user helpdesk** who will
 - maintain the connection between the user, the single provider and the platform coordinating teams
 - oversee the global workflow of all the proposals in all their stages
- centralized user helpdesk will be supported by platform helpdesks (one for each platform) for specific enquiries
- all the processes will be handled **through an IT dashboard handling the proposal workflow** as described below.

2.3.2 MANAGEMENT OF THE ACCESS PROPOSALS

The **proposal workflow** can be schematized as:

- pre-submission interaction with user helpdesk and/or service providers
- submission (user can submit at any time)
- technical feasibility and adequation of the local expertise assessment by facility providers following each deadline
- Peer Review Panel evaluation
- announcement of the results (through automatically generated emails as **access**: 1. granted, 2. not granted – reserved list, above threshold, 3. not granted – below threshold)
- interaction with users granted access (i.e., coordinating provider agrees on dates to deliver access; for multi-platform proposal as many coordinating providers as the number of involved platforms can be designated. The two/three coordinating providers, each with their own specificity, act as a unified team)
- access provision delivered
- data transferred to the user
- monitoring of post-access duties (i.e., user duties: submission of report, submission of the questionnaires for the quality feedback, assessing potential sanctions).

The E-RIHS Access Policy is under preparation and will be published on the E-RIHS ERIC website.

The **timespan** from the proposal submission cut-off deadline to the final evaluation and ranking should last no more than 3 months as specified in Table 4. Different types of accesses might undergo slightly different routes.

Table 4. Various steps in the lifetime of the proposal submission to access E-RIHS ERIC research services.

Pre-submission interaction	Anytime
Submission	any time until the cut-off deadline
Feasibility	within 2 weeks from the cut-off deadline
PRP evaluation	Completed within 2 months from the feasibility check
Communication of the result to user	Automatic emails based on the ranking

The **Peer Review Panel (PRP)** in charge of the scientific evaluation and ranking of all the proposals will operate through a unified modus operandi (see Table 5 for evaluation criteria). These criteria were designed within the IPERION HS project and are currently being updated based on collective experience as part of the Access Policy (D5.6) and the implementation of first call for access of E-RIHS ERIC. It is foreseen that in E-RIHS ERIC the PRP is unique according to expert disciplines for all three platforms and operates through a dedicated IT dashboard.

2.3.3 IT DASHBOARD FOR THE MANAGEMENT OF ACCESS PROPOSALS

To facilitate the management in the provision of RI services, a data management system (system of dashboards) that collects and organizes data is set up with a precise workflow. As an online visualization tool, the system is composed of 4 dashboards, projected to assist:

- **User**
- **Provider**
- **Reviewer**
- **User Helpdesk (UH)**

at each separate organizational step of the access experience. Each dashboard manages different levels of permission to access the information and data therein. Automatic responses within the dashboard system are used to verify the status of each proposal and service requested, from application submission throughout the selection process and alerting as to the necessary actions to be taken. Furthermore, the system provides necessary numbers, statistics, and information for the quality evaluation.

The system is currently under development and will be available in the E-RIHS ERIC Catalogue of Services platform, which is also accessible from the [E-RIHS.eu](https://www.e-rihs.eu) website. At the time of writing, the guidelines for its use are under construction and will be definite once the Catalogue of Services of E-RIHS ERIC is online. Its functioning will be described in the *E-RIHS IP Deliverable D5.4 E-RIHS ERIC Catalogue of Services*. In due time, precise instructions will be developed for each role (i.e., User, Provider, Reviewer, User Helpdesk). It is worth mentioning that one key takeaway from the IPERION HS FIXLAB experience is that the “provider” role should be divided into two main functions: scientific and administrative. Administrative staff must have access to all proposals for their facility to keep track of its activity. Cumulative email contacts (that includes more than one expert) per technique seems to ensure timely responsiveness on the provider side (e.g., in case of sickness, maternity leave, workload, etc).

The developed written guidelines for the use of dashboard should ideally be developed also in the form of short videos explaining the procedures step-by-step. Moreover, specific training modules should be developed to improve the user experience and augment the preparedness of the service providers. The training modules/videos should be regularly communicated, reposted, advertised especially but not only close to the submission deadline. These steps will contribute to the smooth provision of the services.

2.4 GUIDELINES FOR HS Academy

E-RIHS ERIC is committed to the delivery of exceptional heritage science training at a global level. The training activities will be organized under an umbrella label “#HSAcademy” (Figure 6). For HS Academy guidance document see Annex 4.1.

Fig. 6: HS Academy logo

HS Academy aims to provide online and in-presence training events and provides open access materials on various topics, including but not limited to art conservation, art history, architectural history and criticism, theory, restoration, digitalization, chemistry, physics, informatics and other studies applied to cultural heritage. The initiative covers a wide range of cutting-edge training opportunities in Heritage Science and has two main objectives:

- **outreach** to potential users and inform them of available E-RIHS services;
- provide **training** on Heritage Science and E-RIHS for those working in or engaging with research infrastructure.

Training activities and FAIR training resources will be available in English and open to an international audience.

2.4.1 PROCEDURAL CONSISTENCY WITHIN HS ACADEMY

The experience of organizing training events, collecting and making available training materials in open access, is essential for the training activities of the E-RIHS community. Detailed training strategy will be described in *E-RIHS IP Deliverable D4.5 Revised E-RIHS Training Strategy*. In brief, diverse training modules as

illustrated in Figure 7 can be delivered all through a unique access point, following the cycle of activities as illustrated in Figure 8.

Fig. 7: HS Academy training activities

Fig. 8: Guidelines for the FAIRification of the training resources

The delivery and organization of training events (e.g., workshops, lectures, webinars, doctoral schools and training camp) should be coordinated by a training facility within the Central Hub where there will be a dedicated team of training staff working to ensure that training goals are met.

The yearly agenda of training activities by E-RIHS should be jointly defined by CNN and the training staff at the Central Hub. Specific tasks and responsibilities of National Nodes for the procedures of organization and delivery of national/local E-RIHS training initiatives should be agreed. E-RIHS will focus on partnerships with other initiatives, organisations, and projects to share best practice, avoid duplication and attain maximum impact. Hence, training delivery will build on already existing training activity and capacity within the E-RIHS community. To align the adopted procedures in a long-term perspective, HS Academy developed specific guidelines for the Central Hub regarding the delivery of training events and the sustainability of post-event training resources. All the delivered training resources should be FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.

2.4.2 METHODOLOGY TO DELIVER ONLINE TRAINING ACTIVITIES

The delivery of online training events, e.g. webinars, lectures or user meeting events, is organized into series (called editions for lectures). Commonly, the series comprises from 5 to 10 singular events, each of them dedicated to a specific topic, organized regularly (e.g. monthly) over a year/academic year. Specific series of

events may be organized in collaboration with other initiatives or projects, following the same methodology as applies to all the types of online training events by HS Academy.

The developed framework of activities for launching the series of online training events (webinars and lectures), with the steps to follow and the related timeline, is illustrated in Figure 9.

FRAMEWORK TO LAUNCH THE ONLINE SERIES TRAINING EVENTS

Fig. 9: Framework to launch the online series training events

The specific workflow the delivery of each singular event of the series (one webinar, one lecture) is illustrated in Figure 10.

Fig. 10: Workflow for the online singular events

2.4.3 METHODOLOGY TO DELIVER IN-PRESENCE TRAINING EVENTS

The in-presence training events of HS Academy include on-site training camps, doctoral summer schools and workshops. The below-reported framework of activities applies to the organization and delivery of the following training events:

- On-site training camps in presence;
- Doctoral summer schools in presence or in a hybrid form (in presence and online);
- Workshops in presence or in a hybrid form (in presence and online).

FRAMEWORK OF ACTIVITIES TO DELIVER IN-PRESENCE TRAINING ACTIVITIES

Fig. 11: Framework to activities to deliver in-presence training events

2.4.4 FAIRIFICATION OF THE TRAINING RESOURCES

The long-term vision for HS Academy is to create a digital platform that contains training for many of the skills that heritage scientists working within and engaging with E-RIHS will need to form an effective relationship with the research infrastructure. This will require training resources to become digitally identifiable objects with PIDs.

For this purpose, E-RIHS will adopt the scheme developed in IPERION HS and H2IOSC project, followed also by other research infrastructure ([Elixir](#), DARIAH, CLARIN etc.) for FAIRification of delivered training resources. The recommended steps for FAIRification of E-RIHS training resources are reported below.

Fig. 12: Workflow for FAIRification of E-RIHS ERIC training resources

2.5 Communication

The communication will adhere to the developed E-RIHS visual identity. The communication officers at Central Hub will oversee populating and maintaining updated the new E-RIHS website. The communication strategy is described in *E-RIHS IP Deliverable D6.2 Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Strategy of E-RIHS ERIC*.

2.5.1 THE COMMUNICATION MODEL

E-RIHS is a distributed research infrastructure with multiple facilities across Europe and cooperation at the global level. E-RIHS ERIC, with a Central Hub seated in Florence (Italy), will comprise numerous National Nodes (NN) and several observers. Such a large and distributed infrastructure requires a consolidated system of external and internal communication. In recent years, E-RIHS experimented with a communication model and a workflow to manage such complexity (<https://zenodo.org/records/6396957>).

It is proposed that the management body is the **Communication Officers Network (CON)**, composed of one or more communication officer(s) representatives of each NN. The CON has the role of:

- defining and periodically revising the communication strategy
- scheduling communication activities according to the E-RIHS ERIC annual programme and budget
- ensuring consistent communication in terms of voice, branding, messaging, and frequency at the central and national level
- amplifying the E-RIHS messages inside the community of the NNs, possibly translating them into the national languages
- defining and periodically monitoring the KPIs related to the communication.

The CON is chaired by the E-RIHS Communication Officer of the Central Hub, who manages the network and coordinates the communication activities at the central level. The CON discusses and implements the objectives of the E-RIHS communication strategy.

It should be considered that most of the CON members possibly do not have structured training in communication. For this reason, it will be fundamental to organize online, and in-person training events focused on communication with practical sessions. These could be delivered under the HS Academy label in cooperation with other Research Infrastructures. It will also be possible to customize them according to the needs of each NN.

The communication flow between the Central Hub and the NNs is a two-way flow. The Central Hub and the NNs share objectives and information and monitor together the communication performances to improve the quality and effectiveness of the activities.

The proposed workflow can be schematized as follows:

- the news of international interest or interest to the Heritage Science community at large are posted on the E-RIHS ERIC channels and reposted on the NNs channels (in English or the national language)
- the news of national or local (institutional) interest is posted first on the NN channels and then reposted on the E-RIHS ERIC channels. In case the NN does not have its channels, the NN could contact the E-RIHS Communication Office and propose the publication of the news.

The Central Hub has the role of coordinator and supervisor of E-RIHS communication activities. Building on the EMSO ERIC experience, the CON members **meet three/four times per year** to discuss the communication strategy, to verify its effectiveness and propose modifications.

Fig. 13: Communication workflow

Expanding the scope, the internal communication flow includes the following actors:

- Researchers
- Individual institutions/facilities
- National Nodes (NNs)
- Central Hub

In this scenario, the flow operates circularly as described below:

- Researchers share relevant scientific outputs such as research results, publications, and collaboration, with their respective institutions that pass the news to the NN
- The institutions then relay this information to the National Node (NN)
- For news of national or local relevance, the NN publishes it on its website and social media and asks the Central Hub to repost it
- In the case of news that holds international relevance, the NN has two options. It can either publish the news on its website and social media platforms and request the Central Hub to repost it, or it can directly request the Central Hub to post the news on the E-RIHS ERIC website and social media, and subsequently repost it on the national channels.

The checklist for the organization of events and the handbook for the website management are attached as Annex.

2.6 Monitoring (KPIs)

The E-RIHS ERIC will support and facilitate all activities, including the work of the CNN and the National Nodes represented in it. Therefore, it will provide the monitoring of quality management procedures to be adopted by the National Nodes and partner facilities. The Central Hub will provide all assessment procedures and will support their implementation and monitoring at each National Node through periodic reporting for the quality audit of existing E-RIHS partners and their services and the quality assessment of prospective new partners and their services. Processes to grant external organizations, services, projects, and proposals the

endorsement or support by E-RIHS will also be monitored. The adoption and narratives of set key performance indicators, will be refined through the experience gained as an operational RI to help establish best practices. The Central Hub will oversee the monitoring of the quality of E-RIHS following the procedures and KPI's described in *E-RIHS IP Deliverable D3.5 E-RIHS Quality System Implementation Plan*.

2.7 Risk Management

E-RIHS is committed to implementing a strategic, consistent, and structured enterprise-wide approach to Risk Management to effectively manage opportunities for gain and minimise the impact of threats causing losses. When it comes to identifying errors and malfunctions in the RI, the Central Hub is essential. It can track and monitor the performance of the Central Hub and each National Node, identify irregularities and departures from regular operation, and start the proper recovery processes to bring the system back to a stable condition. The distributed infrastructure's resilience and reliability are increased by this centralized fault detection and recovery capability.

The Risk Management of E-RIHS is based on based on the International Standard ISO 31000:2018(E) – “Risk Management Guidelines” published 2018. The Risk Management Strategy is described in the *E-RIHS IP Deliverable D3.3 E-RIHS IP Risk Management Strategy*. Annex A of that document includes the updated E-RIHS ERIC **Risk Management Framework**, that is, set of components that provide the foundations and organizational arrangements for designing, implementing, monitoring, reviewing and continually improving Risk Management throughout the organization. Annex B of that document contains the updated E-RIHS ERIC **Risk Management Policy**, which includes the (i) identification of levels at which different Risk Management decisions are to be taken, persons to fulfil this responsibility how such decisions are taken - levels of authority, levels of delegation, methods for upwards and downward communication of decisions about risk(s) and the (ii) responsibility for the ongoing maintenance and amendment of the Risk Management methodology and the communication and promotion of the ERIC's approach to Risk Management.

Fig. 14: Risk Management process

The Management of Risks relating to the ERIC overall is the responsibility of the Central Hub. All risks relating to the ERIC overall must be escalated to this level. It will also have overall responsibility for the ongoing definition and compliance with the Risk Manual throughout the ERIC. Section 6.2 of the Risk Management Frameworks establishes when a Risk identified at national level may be escalated to the Central Hub level.

The scheme below (Figure 15) summarizes the hierarchy of Risk Management activities of E-RIHS ERIC.

	Identify	Own/Manage	Monitor	Escalation	Communication and Consultation	
Central Hub	Any participating organisation may identify any risk at any time. Ownership will be allocated according to the procedures adopted by the National Node and/or the Central Hub	Risks relating to the ERIC overall including reputational risks	All risks owned / managed by the organisation also all risks at any level which are deemed to have an impact on that organisation		Report all risks deemed to have an impact on National Hubs or individual partner	
National Node		Risks relating to the National Implementation of the ERIC including reputational risks			Notify all risks deemed to have a potential impact at Multi-National Level	Report all risks deemed to have an impact on one or more individual partners
Individual Partners		Risks relating to the Partner organisation and to research activities undertaken by the Partner			Notify all risks deemed to have a potential impact at National level	

Fig. 15: The hierarchy of Risk Management activities of E-RIHS ERIC

Risk Management responsibilities are detailed in Section 12 of the Risk Management Policy. At the level of the Central Hub, it establishes a Risk Management Committee responsible, amongst others, of the implementation of the principles, actions and requirements of the Risk Management plan and monitoring its implementation within the E-RIHS ERIC overall. A specific role of E-RIHS Risk Manager will be allocated to one of the members of the Central Hub. A Risk Management Database, which constitutes an enhanced version of the conventional Risk Register, will be maintained by the Central Hub and will be accessible to all participants in E-RIHS ERIC.

This Risk Management Database will contain a detailed risk inventory, classified in the categories established in Section 17 of the Risk Management Strategy:

- a) Financial – impact on E-RIHS finances
- b) Operational – impact on provision of E-RIHS products, projects, and services
- c) Reputational – impact on the professional and scientific reputation of E-RIHS and its membership overall and on its wider general credibility
- d) Physical/Safety – impact on the safety and well-being of people
- e) Regulatory/Legal – impact on E-RIHS of regulatory exposure
- f) People – impact on corporate knowledge / continuity / professional development and welfare of individuals

According to Section 3.2 of the Risk Management Framework, a risk will always best expressed in the form:

“There is a Risk that [xxxxxxx] will occur, with the consequence for the ERIC/National Node/Partner/Artefact of [zzzzzzzzzz]”

In order to test the Risk Management strategy and obtain preliminary results to facilitate its application as soon as the ERIHS ERIC starts, a workshop for the initial identification of risks has been carried out on September 16th, under Task 3.3. In the workshop, the coordinators of the National Nodes have participated in a brainstorming exercise to identify the main risks in the 6 categories. The risks identified by the attending National Node coordinators were gathered by means of an interactive board and have been later reformulated and incorporated into the Risk Management database (see Figure 16 below), along with some initial risk mitigation measures.

Upon setting up of the Central Hub, the database will be completed by the Risk Management Committee and the E-RIHS Risk Manager, identifying new risks, allocating risk owners, and carrying out the risk analysis and evaluation according to the Risk Management Strategy.

ID		Identification			Analysis				Evaluation	Treatment	
unique identifier	Date	Risk name	Description	Category	Impact	Probability	Proximity	Score	Planned Response	Risk mitigation measures	Owner
R0001		1-3 words	D3.3 pag. 16 There is a risk of Central Hub financial resources turning out to be inadequate to support smooth operation of the ERIC.	Financial						(a) Ask NNs for in kind contribution (b) Adjustment of operational costs and, consequently, the ERIC budget to inflation	
R0002			There is a Risk that the ERIC fails to attract new categories of users & address new needs, resulting in a widening gap between heritage research and E-RIHS offer, such that E-RIHS loses relevance over time	Reputational						conduct user outreach and re-appraise the user strategy	
R0003			There is a Risk that one National Node leaves the ERIC, with the consequence for the ERIC/National Node/Partner/Artefact of reduction of the economic contribution	Financial						(a) increase other members contribution (b) reduce the ERIC costs	
R0004			There is a Risk that projects are not financially feasible, with the consequence for the ERIC/National Node/Partner/Artefact not able to implement the project.	Financial						Need of Cost Benefit Analysis	
R0005			There is a risk for national node to loose financial support due to various reasons like lack of high quality publications. Frequently services offered to the end users have technical character not scientific.	Financial						Evaluation criteria might include also fair distribution of services	
R0006			here is a risk of loosing financial by the national node due to too many services implemented outside the country. the distribution of heritage resources is not uniform across Europe. Some countries might not want to pay for research in other countries.	Financial						evaluation criteria might include also fair distribution of services	

Fig. 16: Risk Management Database with initial identification of risks.

3 CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable presents various workflows and procedures regarding the key activities covered by the Central Hub staff. It is a living document that needs to be updated and revised regularly. As a part of good practice, internal and external training on various tools and procedures should be planned and performed. It is of utmost importance to regularly implement the section of frequently asked questions on the ERIC’s website, develop dedicated guidelines for the users and establish a structured and well-functioning User Helpdesk.

4 ANNEXES

4.1 HS Academy guidance

The HS Academy is an E-RIHS ERIC service offering a suite of activities to engage, train and inform scholars and professionals in the field, and those with an interest in heritage science.

1. Types of HS Academy training events

HS Academy training events may be (i) in-person, on-line or hybrid, (ii) paid-for or free-of-charge, (iii) enrolling participants on first-come-first-served or other bases (e.g. pre-existing knowledge), and may involve (non-exhaustive list):

1. Events, such as:
 - a. One-off activities: invited lectures etc.
 - b. Continuous training activities: series of lectures, podcasts etc.
 - c. One-off or annual events of limited duration: summer schools, winter schools, bootcamps, training camps, workshops (attached to a conference or not), hackathons etc.
2. Courses, such as:
 - a. Master- and doctoral-level, as well as professional courses aimed at students and professionals (e.g. in the frame of Continuous Professional Education – CPD) and delivered over the course of several weeks or months, without active involvement of the E-RIHS ERIC in the delivery of teaching.
 - b. Master- and doctoral-level, as well as professional courses aimed at students and professionals (e.g. CPD), with active involvement of the E-RIHS ERIC in the delivery of teaching as a partner (e.g. EU Marie Curie or Erasmus projects).

HS Academy training activities may be organised in the frame of an educational institution and offered to students enrolled in e.g. master or doctoral courses and if so, they must allow for enrolment of participants who are not regularly enrolled in such master or doctoral courses.

2. Approval and reporting

For a training activity to be recognised as a HS Academy activity and labelled as an E-RIHS activity, it must, as a minimum, clearly communicate to the E-RIHS ERIC Central Hub the following for approval, in principle at least three months in advance of the start of the training event:

1. Title
2. Responsible organiser (name and institution)
3. Duration and timing
4. Budget and funding mechanism (e.g. fees, project funding, institutional funding, E-RIHS ERIC funding)
5. Alignment with the E-RIHS Training Strategy
6. Description of the course:
 - a. Content
 - b. Instructors
 - c. Location
7. Enrolment conditions and instructions
8. Maximum number of participants

9. Fees (and, potentially, financial help available for the participants to attend, e.g. bursaries and if so, the process to request it)
10. Mode of delivery: in-person, on-line, hybrid
11. Scope, clarifying:
 - a. (i) who is the activity meant for;
 - b. (ii) what is the required level of knowledge/skills for participants to be able to benefit from the training event.
12. Learning outcomes, clarifying what skills and/or knowledge the participants will learn
13. Deliverables, such as teaching materials, recordings etc., that will be made available open access as part of the E-RIHS HS Academy offer.

All HS Academy activities must, organise an exit questionnaire, reporting (as a minimum):

- a. Number of participants and their professional backgrounds (conservator, restorer, artist, STEM, SSH, other),
- b. Level of satisfaction with the course content (scale 1-10),
- c. Level of satisfaction with the course delivery (scale 1-10),
- d. Level of satisfaction with the course organisation (scale 1-10),
- e. Usefulness for their daily work/study (scale 1-10),
- f. Content liked least and why (open text),
- g. Content liked most and why (open text),
- h. Country of residence,
- i. Age.

Reporting requirements:

1. The questionnaire results
2. Financial report

The above must be reported to the E-RIHS ERIC Central Hub after the completion of the activity. This completes the training event.

3. Funding and finance

HS Academy training events can be funded in different ways, e.g. through:

- E-RIHS ERIC budget,
- E-RIHS National Node budget,
- Institutional budget,
- Fees,
- Third-party funding (Horizon Europe, national grants, etc.).

The training provider, E-RIHS ERIC or National Node should look to apply for external funding in the first instance, to alleviate the financial pressure on the participants as much as possible.

4. Education

E-RIHS ERIC takes part in continuous education of master students or PhD students, e.g. through access. This is not an HS Academy activity.

On the other hand, if such education is part of an E-RIHS ERIC-delivered course (point 1.2.b), it is an HS Academy activity.

5. Teaching materials and acknowledgement

Stakeholders are welcome to re-use training materials produced by any category of training activity labelled as HS Academy and made available open access, in their teaching, provided that E-RIHS is acknowledged.

4.2 Checklist for organization of events

Establish the aim of the event

Establish the total budget of the event

Agenda and registration (Central Hub – dedicated event officer or communication officer)

- Prepare the agenda of the event
- Draft an invitation letter for partners, speakers, etc...
- Launch a save-the-date by email
- Create a registration form online through Eventbrite – download the list of participants, remind to set up questions about days in which people are going to participate (for multiple day event), dietary restriction, participation in social events
- Reserve hotel, plane, and travel accommodations for special guests (speakers, authorities, SAB) if applicable

Venue (organizer)

- Choose a location and verify if there are rooms for general meeting (verify the maximum capacity), working groups, SC, GB, etc...
- Reserve the venue in time
- Verify accessibility and review security needs
- Contact the ceremonial office or the person in charge for organizing the meeting in the venue
- Verify the parking area, extra parking permits, taxi, bus, etc...
- Distribute the map of the venue and information about transportation
- Organize the registration and welcome area
- If necessary, recruit welcome staff
- Plan functional and aesthetically pleasing lighting design (if necessary)
- Check the presence (or rent) a video-projection system and wi-fi (if necessary)
- Check the presence (or rent a sound and possibly video) system configuration and request for the design of wiring system for power supply, coordination with other suppliers, management of logistic, set up and system check and technical assistance during the event, dismantling and delivery
- If possible, ensure / rent / buy niceties: Plants and flowers for rooms
- Verify the cleanliness of the venue
- Verify if there is toilet paper and soap in the restrooms

Accommodation and food (organizer)

- Catering (ask for cost estimates for coffee breaks, lunch, cocktails, with or without waiters, etc...)
- Water for speakers, moderator, ... on the main desk
- Organize a social dinner (give information about the cost and the location of the restaurant / place well in advance to the participants)

Communication strategy (coordination office)

- Create a news event on the website and social media profiles,
- Contact a press officer to create a press release and collaborate with the local media / tv / press
- or create a list of media / tv / press contacts, prepare media kit materials (a folder with press release, speakers' info, photos, etc.), organize interviews with keynote speakers,

Promotional / communication materials (organizer together with coordination office)

- Create name badges (plus blank name badges)
- Prints of the programme of the event
- Create event folders with promotional materials (programme, brochure or flyer, block notes and a pen, event evaluation form)
- Create directional signs (to event, to bathroom, regarding access)
- Create signs to hang at the doors to indicate the meeting inside the rooms
- Design event posters / roll ups
- Prepare a welcome event slide / video for video projection during breaks

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- Create reserved signs for special guests and authorities on the desk
- Design and print keynote speakers table tent cards (“cavaliere”)
- Print the event evaluation form and insert in the event folder
- Block notes and Pens
- Gadgets
- Flyers, posters, brochure, cards on the welcome desk
- Create a media consent form or include it in the registration form

For international meeting with politicians (organizer)

- Ask for patronage of public institutions
- If necessary, notify Police, Ambulance Service and Fire Brigade
- Look for sponsorships
- Simultaneous interpreters’ services (translators, cabins, headphones for participants)

Social events (organizer)

- Organize a social dinner
- Organize a tour (museums, attractions, of the city, etc...)

Follow up (organizer together with coordination office)

- Send thank-you and acknowledgement letters to sponsors, volunteers, speakers, donors, the media.
- Post-event publicity in the media
- Reach out to event participants – thank them for participating and promote your ongoing programs and how they can support you throughout the year by joining, volunteering, or making a sustaining donation.
- Collect evaluation forms during the event (or distribute the relevant KPIs questionnaire) and analyse the feedback of the participants

4.3 Handbook for CMS managers E-RIHS.eu website

HANDBOOK FOR CMS MANAGERS

E-RIHS WEBSITE

Version v1.0 – April 2024

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Concept of the E-RIHS.eu website

A new Concept for the E-RIHS website

The new E-RIHS website has a new personality and a new tone of voice.

At E-RIHS, we apply an innovative, interdisciplinary approach to answer the specific needs of cultural and natural heritage assets and improve their understanding and preservation.

Our mission is to deliver integrated access to expertise, data, and technologies for protecting heritage.

Our motto is ***“E-RIHS. Connecting heritage to science”*** (<https://www.e-rihs.eu/e-rihs-survey-new-slogan/>).

Page structure

We have defined a new structure for the website, which means how the different pages are organized and linked. It is a question of user experience and Search Engine Optimization (SEO).

The current sitemap has the following organization:

At the moment of writing, some pages are in progress and/or hidden (such as Help Desk & FAQ and DIGILAB).

Tone of voice

We decided to use a casual tone of voice to express our aim of engaging professionals and the public at large in the heritage science community and E-RIHS activities. Protecting heritage is a universal duty. Cultural heritage is the legacy of our past, and it is our responsibility to preserve it for future generations. It is also a shared responsibility, as heritage belongs to all of us, regardless of our nationality, ethnicity, or religion.

Users – Login and management

To log in and manage the E-RIHS website, it is necessary to create an account as a user. The user can have different roles. Each role is allowed to perform a set of tasks.

Administrator – who has access to all the administration features. The administrator can attribute roles and delete users.

Editor – who can publish and manage posts including posts of other users, edit or delete pages, manage categories, moderate comments, upload files.

Author – who can publish and manage their own posts.

Contributor – who can write and manage their own posts but cannot publish them.

You as a user have an account composed of an email and a password. You can recover the password at any time by clicking on the “Lost your password?” string. You can also decide to remember the login data.

You can log in from the following URL: <https://www.e-rihs.eu/wp-login.php>

Backend (Frontend and Dashboard)

Description of the backend

The backend of the E-RIHS website is a WordPress dashboard.

On the lateral, left menu, you will find some additional plugins (see further).

The backend is integrated with the Divi theme and the Divi Builder.

You can edit content visually or traditionally, with the default WP editor and Gutenberg editor.

If you use the Divi Builder, you can edit the contents from the front end.

Deliverable D2.5

Once logged in, you can choose on the top menu “Enable Visual Builder”, and you can easily edit all the blocks and modules which compose the page.

You can also choose the string “edit page” from the top black menu and the system will open a page with a purple button “Edit with the Divi Builder”, you click on the button, and you edit visually.

If you choose “Visual edit builder”, your screen presents different boxes (blue, green, grey) that refer to different levels of editing (grey for text, green and blue for the structure...)

At the bottom of the page, you will find a purple hamburger menu. If you click on the menu, different icons appear (image below):

On the left: Builder settings – wireframe view (to see the structure of the page) – zoom – desktop view – tablet view – mobile view.

In the middle: + (to choose a layout) – save to the library – delete – x (to close the hamburger menu) – Page settings – Editing history – Portability.

On the right: Find – Layers – Divi Builder Helper – Save.

For more information, visit the website: <https://www.elegantthemes.com/gallery/divi/> and <https://www.elegantthemes.com/no-code-design/>

Pages

You can create a new page or edit or delete an existing page.

You have two ways of creating a new page:

1. From the lateral, left menu of the dashboard, you can access the section related to the pages of the website. You can click on “All pages” or “Add new”.
2. From the top menu, you can click on “+New” and select “page”.

To add a new page

You can use the existing layouts. Go to the dashboard and choose “add a new page” from the lateral or top menu. Click on “Use Divi Builder”. The system will show you three choices:

Build from scratch – Choose a premade layout – Clone existing page.

Deliverable D2.5

Select “Choose a premade layout” or “clone an existing page”. If you click on “choose a premade layout”, then select “Your existing pages”. Choose the one that best suits your purpose.

To edit an existing page

You have two ways to modify a page:

1. From the dashboard, select “Pages” and then “All pages”, select the page you want to modify and click on “edit”.

2. From the front end, go to the page you want to edit and click on “Edit page” or “Enable Visual Builder” from the top, black menu. Select and edit or add the module you want to add or change (text, accordion...).

Some pages are composed of different elements and use specific plugins. To edit these parts, you must select the plugin on the left menu of the dashboard and use them, as explained below:

National Nodes (Dashboard)

If you want to edit or add a National Node, you must use the plugin “National Node” on the Dashboard > lateral, left menu.

Select “add new” and include the information and the images. Set the featured image.

You don’t need to use the Divi Builder. The system will contain the following fields that you can fill in:

- Description
- Node map
- Imagine about
- Partners
- Photo Gallery

When you upload an image, remember to insert the ALT – text.

Deliverable D2.5

Project and collaborations (Dashboard)

If you want to add a new project, you have to use the plugin “Project” on the lateral, left menu.

Comments	Title	Author	Project Categories
Projects	ARCHE – Alliance for Research on Cultural Heritage – Divi	morganti	Current Project
All Projects	Heritage Samples Archives Initiative (HSAI)	morganti	Current Project
Add New	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua – Private	morganti	Current Project
Categories	Lorem ipsum-3 dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua – Private	morganti	Current Project
Tags	Lorem ipsum-4 dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua – Private	morganti	Current Project
Maps	Prova 4	morganti	Completed Project
User Reports	prova 3	morganti	Completed Project
Just publish	prova 2	morganti	Completed Project
Appearance	Prova 1	morganti	Completed Project
Plugins 7	Title	Author	Project Categories
Users			
Tools			
Settings			
ACF			
MC4WP			
SG Optimizer			
SG Security			
Social Apps 1			

You can edit an existing one or click on “add new”. You don’t need to use the Divi Builder, but Gutenberg, WordPress editor. The system will contain the following fields that you can fill in:

- Title
- Text/Summary project
- Coordinator
- Website
- Type of Funding received
- Project Objectives

- Additional resources (Grant Agreement, Duration, EU contribution, ...)
- Link to social (Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn)
- More info – here insert the project website

On the right menu, you must choose the CATEGORIES between “completed project” or “current project” and include specific tags and a featured image. Then click on “publish”.

HS Academy

At the time of writing, the box HS Academy is linked to the HS Academy in IPERION HS (a project funded by the European Union, H2020-INFRAIA-2019-1, under G.A. 871034 and closed on March 31st, 2024).

To add a new “HS Academy opportunity” (dashboard)

Go to the dashboard and click on the lateral or top menu: “+New > HS Academy” or “HS Academy> Add New”. Add the title, the Text, and HS Academy Categories on the right, tag and set a featured image. Check the SEO elements and click to Save draft/Preview or Publish (read the **SEO tips** below). The “HS Academy opportunities” will be published also in the “Users news” section on the page [User Stories](#).

User stories

To add a new “User report” (Dashboard)

Go to the dashboard and click on the lateral or top menu: “Add new user report”.

Add the title, abstract, and the following info:

- User and/or User Group Leader
- ORCID
- Venue
- Organization (to which the user belongs)
- Facility/ies (that means the provider/s who offered the access)
- Technique/s requested (possibly linked to the related webpage of the Catalogue of Services)
- Archive requested (possibly linked to the related webpage of the Catalogue of Services)

You can add the file of the report and include a dynamic gallery. The images should have the following proportion 9:7 (e.g. 786x610), or you can link a video (YouTube o Vimeo).

You can also add Keywords (tags), which will be on the Preview (grey colour).

Deliverable D2.5

To add a new “User experience”

This kind of content is automatically generated from the [YouTube User Experience playlist](#).

To add a new “User news”

It is automatically with the publishing of the HS Academy opportunity (read “*To add a new “HS Academy opportunity”*”).

Publications

When you want to add a new publication, you must choose the “Just publish” plugin from the left menu and click on “Add a new” one. You must fill in the following fields:

Title – abstract – video URL or publication link – publication data – featured image.

Newsroom

If you want to add an event, click “Events” on the left menu.

If can add the title, description, time and date, location, organizer, event website and a featured image. Before creating a new event, you can also insert tags, event categories, venues, and organizers: you will be able to include them in the event and use them for other events.

The venue must be added at the beginning, first to create the event. You find Venue in the Event, in the left menu.

Deliverable D2.5

If you want to change/add a video to the “**Must see**” section, you have to insert a new Video.

Go to the Dashboard > Videos > Add new.

You can choose to upload a file or add a video URL (e.g. YouTube or Vimeo...). We suggest adding a link so as not to make the site heavier.

Write the text and choose your featured image.

If you want to add images to the “**Gallery**” section, first you must create a new “gallery” page:

Click on “add a new page” and then “Clone existing page”. E.g. choose “HS Academy gallery”. Edit the webpage including the images you want to add.

Go to the “[Gallery](#)” webpage, enable the Visual Builder and click on and open the purple hamburger menu at the bottom of the page. On the left you must click on the wireframe view.

The webpage will show you the structure and you can add a new row (green) and choose the three-column structure.

You have to alternate the two modules: “Blurb” and “Who we are”.

In the “Blurb” you must upload an image in the “Image & Icon” string and add the links to the “Title Link URL” and the “Module Link URL”, choosing to open them in the same window.

In the “who we are” you add the title of the gallery and a description in the text field.

To upload one or more images on the Gallery, choose the Gallery you prefer (<https://www.e-rihs.eu/meetings-gallery/> or <https://www.e-rihs.eu/hs-academy-gallery/>), select “Edit visual builder”, select grey box

and insert the images.

Participate

If you want to edit this page, click on “Enable Visual Builder”, or “edit” from the list of the pages.

Click on “Edit with the Divi Builder”.

Click on the section or block you want to edit and make the changes.

In this page there are two “accordion” modules.

If you want to change the “accordion” module, click on the “setting icon”, click on the row you want to modify or on “add New Accordion Item”.

When done, open the purple hamburger menu at the bottom of the page and save (green button on the right).

E-RIHS IP

The page is composed of different tabs with the following information:

The project – has the same link as the main page (<https://www.e-rihs.eu/the-project/>). It is composed of text that you can edit through the Divi Builder

Work programme – if you want to add or edit the text, click on “Enable Visual Builder”, and edit with the Divi Builder.

If you want to edit the accordion, click on the settings icon of the accordion, select the item, and change the text from the tab “content” or the icon from the tab “design”. Save with the green tick. Open the purple hamburger menu at the bottom of the page and click on the button “save” on the right.

Project outcomes – the tab contains the deliverables of the project. If you want to link a deliverable to the text, click on Enable Visual Builder, click on the text block, select the text: a grey menu will appear above the text, choose the link icon and digit the URL of the file. Then save as usual.

Partners – if you want to edit a partner, click on Enable Visual Builder, click on the blurb module settings, and change the title, the text or the image/logo. Click on the purple hamburger menu and save with the button on the right.

The IP Central Office – If you want to add a card to the team or edit or delete one of them, click on Enable Visual Builder, click on the Flip Cards Settings, and fill in the content of the front and of the back and add an image. Then click on the green tick to save, open the hamburger menu to update the page.

Posts

When you want to write a post (news), you can follow the procedure below. It will be published on HomePage and in NEWS <https://www.e-rihs.eu/news/>.

Add Title, Text, Category, Tags, SEO elements.

You don't have to set font, dimension, or style: they are automatically set up. If you need, you can add additional modules to the layout.

Images must be of good quality and have the following proportions: 9:7 (eg. 786x610).

You can use these tools to calculate the ratio of your image: [Simplify ratio](#) or [Screen Size calculator](#).

It is crucial to include the right categories and tags.

Categories are meant to broadly group posts, they are general topics (eg. Conference, Video, etc...). Categories are hierarchical, which means it is possible to create subcategories.

Don't add categories unless it is truly necessary. When you need to add a new one, select the categories from the list you can find on the left menu (Posts – Categories) and add a new category.

When you add a category, you must write the name of the category (starting with a capital letter) and the slug, which is its permalink.

By default, the category will be added as a Top-level Category. This means that it is not a subcategory. To create subcategories, toggle off the switch for Top level Category and choose the top-level category you want this subcategory associated with.

Tags are meant to describe specific details of the post. They are more specific keywords. They are normally made up of one or two words. They are not hierarchical. For example, if you wrote a post about a book, then you could use tags to describe the author, publisher, and topics covered. Tags improve the usability of your site by helping visitors quickly find a specific subject without needing to scan all your posts.

You can add new tags (as for the categories) or choose from tags that you have previously created by typing the first few letters of a tag, and then clicking the tag you want to use.

How to add a new post

You can add a new post from the dashboard. Click on "Add new"

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When you click on “Add new”, a webpage is open. You must click on “Use default editor”.

Include a title (standard format), a subtitle in H5 style, and the text as a paragraph.

When done, you must choose a “category” on the right-hand side of the page under the “Post settings”. All the news must be categorized. Please take care of using the existing ones which are standardized, as explained above. Upload a featured image.

When done, click on “save draft”, check the “preview” and then publish the news.

If you want to publish news about HS Academy opportunities (training or activities, such as Lecture, User Meeting...) you must create another post in the HS Academy section (described at HS Academy paragraph).

Remember: You cannot copy and paste the same content. The two pieces of text content MUST always be different. On the same website, you can never have two identical pages.

Media

You can manage photos and video from “Media” on the lateral, left menu.

Click on Library and you will overview all the media already uploaded.

If you want to add a new media, click on “Add new”. Drop the files to upload or “select files” from the computer.

The maximum size of the file is 256 MB, but it depends on the use of the file. If possible, upload files with a medium resolution.

When uploaded, you can edit additional information:

Alternative Text (alt text) – Typically used for screen readers and to improve the user experience for the visually impaired, alt text is the descriptive text you’ll see if an image doesn’t load, or when you roll over an image on a webpage. It must be no longer more than 140 characters.

To Write Good “Alt Text”

Add alt text to all non-decorative images.

Keep it short and descriptive, like a tweet.

Don't include "image of" or "photo of".

Leave alt text blank if the image is purely decorative.

It's not necessary to add text in the Title field.

More suggestions [here](#).

If this same image was used in a different context: an article focusing on royal fashion in the XX century England an appropriate alt text could be "King Henry VIII of England wearing a fur-trimmed hat and cape, bedazzled shirt and golden jewelry."

HTML:

```

```

([Source of King Henry VIII of England Image](#))

Title – It is an internal resource and isn't usually visible to external users.

Caption – Captions are brief text descriptions that you can add to your images. They are typically used to provide additional details about an image.

Description – This is the descriptive text that shows up on your image attachment page. Any time you upload an asset to your website (be it an image, PDF, video, or audio file) WordPress, by default, creates a page to host just that piece of content. That page gets its own URL (separate from the image URL described above) which can contain more information about a graphic than may be necessary or relevant on its parent page.

File URL – Once you've uploaded an asset to the WordPress media library, a URL is created automatically. This image URL is simply the location of an asset on the server. Image URLs contain filenames, which is one reason you must name your files intelligently.

You can choose the level of compression (None – Low – Medium – High).

You can download the file or delete permanently.

The image must have:

A maximum size of 256 MB and

9:7 proportion (eg. 786x610).

You can use these tools to calculate the ratio of your image: [Simplify ratio](#) or [Screen Size calculator](#).

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It is important to attribute the proper [Creative Commons licenses](#) for the images uploaded to the website. Creative Commons means that some rights are reserved. The authors decide which type of use can be done with the data. Now, a specific field doesn't exist. When uploading an image in the library, you can include this information in the description or in the copy of the News/opportunity/event.

To choose the best Creative Commons license for publications and research data, you can use the tools [License chooser](#) (beta version) or [B2SHARE license selector wizard](#).

Plugins and tools

Just publish

The plugin "Just Publish" manages the "Focus on research" section in the "Publications" webpage under the "Resources" menu.

To add a new one or change an existing one, go to the lateral, left menu and click on "Just publish" or "Add new".

In case you want to add a new publication, add a title, the abstract (pick the abstract directly from the publication and consider that the text will be cut), the publication link, the publication date, and the excerpt (a short summary of the content, useful for SEO).

Include a featured image.

Save the draft, have a preview, and then publish the items.

In case you edit an existing publication, at the end remind them to update the item.

Maps

This plugin "Maps" manages the map of the National Nodes, visible at the pages: <https://www.e-rihs.eu/organization-and-governance/> and <https://www.e-rihs.eu/national-nodes/>

To use it, go to the dashboard and click on "Maps" in the lateral, left menu.

In case of changes in the National Nodes' configuration, you can add or delete a country. You can click on "all maps" in the lateral, left menu of the dashboard and click on the blue button "add New Region". Fill out all the fields, save and update. You can also click on the "Region Codes" on the lateral, right menu.

When done, click on "Update".

Video

The plugin "Videos" manages only the videos on the homepage under the section "News". If you want to change or add a video, you can click on "add new", and insert a title, a short description and the URL or the file of the video.

National Nodes

The "National Nodes" plugin on the lateral, left menu of the dashboard manages the description of each National Node. If you want to add a new one, click on "Add new" and fill in the information required: title, description, featured image, map (as described below), a general image of the country, partners (Acronym, Full name linked with the website: e.g. CNR [Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche](#)), a gallery of images related to the activities or tools of the National Nodes.

To add the map, go to Google Maps, search for the country (e.g. Italy), click on "share" and choose "embed a map", copy the html code (e.g. `<iframe src="https://www.google.com/maps/embed?pb=!1m18!1m12!1m3!1d6150904.06966727!2d7.43180541066557!3d41.17007183792992!2m3!1f0!2f0!3f0!3m2!1i1024!2i768!4f13.1!3m3!1m2!1s0x12d4fe82448dd203%3A0xe22cf55c24635e6f!2sit!1s0!3m2!1sen!2sit!4v1696931430202!5m2!1sen!2sit" width="600"`

height="450" style="border:0;" allowfullscreen="" loading="lazy" referrerpolicy="no-referrer-when-downgrade"></iframe>), go back to the “node map” string and copy the code in the **text** field and not in the visual (on top on the box)

Newsletter

You can manage the Newsletter page from:

- Homepage: with DiviBuilder you can upload the text through the text editor (on the grey setting).

- Page Newsletter, from Dashboard > Pages > Newsletter. Here you'll use the WP editor, and you can write the text related to the Newsletter service, choose an image and set the page using Divi builder.

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- The Mailchimp plugin is installed to manage the newsletter. At the moment of writing, we chose a free account with basic functionalities to send and receive contact.
- If you want to know how many leads E-RIHS has, you must go to the left menu and choose “MC4WP”. To download the contacts, you must go to Mailchimp and download the list.

Insight

Google Analytics 4

We choose GA4 as the insight platform.

You can manage and analyze data on the Google Analytics platforms.

Privacy Iubenda

We choose Iubenda for the manage Privacy and Cookies. (For the first year) to change any information, contact communication@e-rihs.eu to write to the IT company and change any information.

Privacy and Cookies Policy

We have also a page dedicated to the Privacy and Cookies Policy.

To upgrade the [privacy policy page](#): browse in the backend, select “Page” on the Dashboard, and look for “Privacy Policy” to upgrade the information. Select “edit” and write in the box.

Remember to write the upgrade date at the end of the page.

We have also a page dedicated to the Privacy and Cookies Policy.

To upgrade the [privacy policy page](#): browse in the backend, select “Page” on the Dashboard, and look for “Privacy Policy” to upgrade the information. Select “edit” and write in the box.

Remember to write the upgrade date at the end of the page. You can choose Divi Builder, too.

SEO Tips

SEO stands for Search Engine Optimization. SEO copywriting is the process of writing content that’s optimized for human readers and search engine algorithms.

Some tips are described below:

- Find the right keywords. You can use online tools such as ICT Keyword Generator
- Find questions people ask – You can use online applications.
- Create engaging and quality content.
- Optimize headers, titles, and meta descriptions. Search engines scan the website, and they will understand the contents better if you are using the correct text hierarchy.
- Headers – Use H1 for the title and H5 for a subtitle. Choose your title carefully and don’t forget to include your main keywords.

- Title tags – ensure every page has a unique title tag that includes the keyword. Keep title tags under 55-60 characters long. Google will cut off longer ones. A title tag is a web element that is part of the code on the top of each page in an area that doesn't show. This area in html is called the "head". The head often has hundreds of lines of code. One of the lines of code in that area is the <title></title>.

- Meta descriptions – keep meta descriptions under 120 characters. Google cuts them off after this point on mobile. Each page's meta description should be unique.
- Make sure all your pages' URL s are clean and clear This means no special characters, no hashtags, no page ID.
- Create easy-to-read content – People use search engines to look for answers or advice. If you write
- An easy-to-read content, it is easier for people to find your content. How to do this? Structure your content with informative headers, include clear paragraphs, start with the main idea first and then add context, examples, etc., use shorter sentences, keep vocabulary simple, avoid jargon, and review readability and tone.
- Include good visuals (videos, images, charts, infographics, etc.) and follow image SEO best practices – use descriptive filenames, compress images to reduce their file size, optimize image alt text. To understand what's displayed in a photo or graphic, search engines look for "alt text," a concise written description (no longer than just a few words) about each image on a website. When writing alt text, be sure to accurately describe what is shown in the image, but also try to include the name of E-RIHS or a few keywords (e.g. Heritage science).
- Include a call to action.
- Utilize anchor text and keep internal linking – Effective anchor text should be used to help users navigate your website and find what they are looking for. Keep in mind that excessive linking or anchors don't really help your readers.
- Build impactful external links – High-quality backlinks from strong domains are a powerful signal to search engines that your content is worth ranking. Choose the valuable ones!
- Track, report, and improve E-RIHS SEO – to make sure the SEO strategy is paying off and verify if we are reaching our KPIs, you must track rankings and analyze the E-RIHS organic traffic on a six-months basis or almost annually.

When you write a post/News/Event/HS Academy opportunity, it's important you look at the **YOAST SEO plugin**.

It's very useful and simple to use.

When you write a text, you can follow the suggestion to write a good SEO-oriented text.

You have a Traffic light and emoji which drive you to the right written.

Useful tools

[Wordpress support guides](#) – to improve your WordPress skills

[Grammarly](#) – Grammar Check tool

[Quillbot](#) – Paraphraser

[DeepL](#) – Translator

[Hemingway App for real-time editing](#) – improve readability

[Short URL](#) or [Bitly](#) – to shorten long links

[Canva](#) – to create visuals

[Unsplash](#), [Flickr](#), or [Pixabay](#) – for royalty-free images

[License chooser](#) or [B2SHARE license selector wizard](#) – to choose the best Creative Commons license for publications and research data.

Glossary

Alt Text – Typically used for screen readers and to improve the user experience for the visually impaired, alt text is the descriptive text you'll see if an image doesn't load, or when you roll over an image on a webpage. Alt text is commonly used in search engine optimisation (SEO) to improve the search engines understanding of the image and context of the page as a whole. (Source: <https://forty8creates.com/51-common-website-terms-defined/>)

Category – Categories provide a helpful way to group related blog posts together. Follow the steps in this guide to create and categorize your posts and display them on your website. Categories keep your posts organized and easy for your readers to navigate. You might want to create categories for different topics you cover on your blog. For example: A food blog may use categories for Breakfast, Lunch, Dinner, and Dessert. (Source: <https://wordpress.com/support/posts/categories/>)

Creative Common Licenses – means that some rights are reserved. The authors decide which type of use can be done with the data.

Hamburger menu – A hamburger menu is typically three stacked lines that indicate a hidden menu. When the lines are clicked or tapped on, a menu slides into view or a drawer appears. The menu holds a list of navigation items or other elements that users can access. (Source: <https://dribbble.com/resources/guide-to-hamburger-menus#:~:text=A%20hamburger%20menu%20is%20typically,elements%20that%20users%20can%20access>)

HTML – is a markup language that defines the basic structure of web pages. (Source: <https://blog.hubspot.com/website/glossary>)

Hyperlink – A hyperlink is generally a link within text linking to another resource. The link could be a webpage or an image and can even open your email for you if the link is to an email address.

Metadata – in HTML is information that describes elements on the webpage but that isn't displayed to users. Metadata is contained in the element of an HTML document and may include information such as the author of the page, the page title, links to CSS elements, and document keywords. This metadata is used by web browsers to help render HTML documents correctly. (Source: <https://blog.hubspot.com/website/glossary>)

Permalink – A *permalink* (i.e., permanent link) is the URL of your page, blog post, and other content on your site. Use the permalink to share a link to your content on social media, in an email, or anywhere else online. This is an example of a permalink for a page: <https://yourgroovydomain.com/my-page>. You can customize the last part of the permalink. (Source: <https://wordpress.com/support/permalinks-and-slugs/>)

Plugin – A plugin will typically be used in your website development to enhance functionality. The plugin saves time by allowing your developer to not rewrite code that someone has already made available. Generally, in the form of a “script”, a plugin can have multiple uses. Be warned, with so many to choose from, plugins and their content aren't made equal. (<https://forty8creates.com/51-common-website-terms-defined/>)

Post – Posts are individual pieces of time-based content on a site. Think of them as articles or updates that you share to offer up new content to your readers. The URL for a post looks like this: <https://yourgroovydomain.com/2024/03/17/post-title/>. You can display posts on your website in different ways, such as on a blog page or grouped by category. (Source: <https://wordpress.com/support/post-vs-page/>)

Search Engine Optimisation (SEO) – To put it simply, and without going into too much detail, SEO, or the service of SEO refers to optimising your website and online activities for search engines to easily find you (index you or rank you). (Sources: <https://forty8creates.com/51-common-website-terms-defined/>)

Tag – Refers to the relevant, specific keywords that are utilized throughout a webpage. (<https://forty8creates.com/51-common-website-terms-defined/>). For example, if you were creating a site that reviews pop culture, you might want to use tags such as science fiction, horror, and action adventure.

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